

Antecedent and Outcome of New Product Development in Leather Industry, Bangkok and Vicinity, Thailand

Authors : Bundit Pungnirund

Abstract : The purposes of this research were to develop and to monitor the antecedent factors which directly affected the success rate of new product development. This was a case study of the leather industry in Bangkok, Thailand. A total of 350 leather factories were used as a sample group. The findings revealed that the new product development model was harmonized with the empirical data at the acceptable level, the statistic values are: $\chi^2=6.45$, $df= 7$, $p\text{-value} = .48856$; $RMSEA = .000$; $RMR = .0029$; $AGFI = .98$; $GFI = 1.00$. The independent variable that directly influenced the dependent variable at the highest level was marketing outcome which had a influence coefficient at 0.32 and the independent variables that indirectly influenced the dependent variables at the highest level was a clear organization policy which had a influence coefficient at 0.17, whereas, all independent variables can predict the model at 48 percent.

Keywords : antecedent, new product development, leather industry, Thailand

Conference Title : ICEMBIT 2014 : International Conference on Economics, Management of Business, Innovation and Technology

Conference Location : London, United Kingdom

Conference Dates : June 29-30, 2014